

HYDROCHEMICAL EVALUATION AND SOURCE IDENTIFICATION OF COASTAL GROUNDWATER PROCESSES

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1. INTRODUCTION

The hydrochemical properties and their genesis of the groundwater of Koyra is determined in this study, which is a region in southwest coastal Bangladesh with an area of 263 km², habituated by approximately 0.20 million people. Hossain et al. (2021) stated residents of southwest coastal Bangladesh suffer various forms of water security risks, specifically groundwater contaminated with saltwater and pollutants, rendering it unsuitable for human use. The substantial literature gap regarding the hydrochemistry of groundwater of the whole Koyra union has been tried to fulfill in this study. The objectives of this study are to determine the drinking water quality and governing factors behind the hydrochemistry of groundwater of Koyra and establish relationships among the water types with respective shallow (<100 m) and deep (100-300 m) aquifers.

2. METHODOLOGY

Twenty Five (25) groundwater samples were collected from the study area in pre-monsoon season and were analyzed in the laboratory according to APHA (1998) methods and physico-chemical parameters along with major ions concentrations were derived. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25 software was implemented, operating with direct oblimin rotation and taking in regard The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy of 0.694 and significant result of Bartlett's test of sphericity. Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was implemented as well incorporating Ward's method with interval of Squared Euclidean Distance. To analyze the dominating hydrochemical facies, a Piper trilinear diagram was employed using the software Aquachem version 13, major ion threshold was set at 15%.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The TDS values exceeded the permissible limit for drinking water suggested by WHO (2022) for 88% of the samples. Concentrations of Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻ and PO₄³⁻ exceeded the permissible limit for 68%, 52%, 80%, 92% and 64% of total samples respectively. PCA of the respective parameters resulted in the extraction of three major components with eigenvalue > 1, cumulatively explaining 74.56% variance of the whole dataset, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Total Variance of extracted components and corresponding loadings using PCA.

Component	Total Variance			Component Matrix			
	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Parameters	Component		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %		1	2	3
1	7.659	51.057	51.057	TDS	0.954		
				EC	0.953		
				Sodium	0.884		
				Sulphate	0.793		
					
				pH	-0.743		
				Depth (m)	-0.732		
1,2				Total Iron	0.640	0.640	
2	1.972	13.149	64.206	Silica		0.729	
3	1.553	10.353	74.559	Phosphate			-0.899

From Table 1, Component 1 showed high positive loading values (>0.6) for these parameters in the following manner: TDS>EC>Na⁺> SO₄²⁻> Ca²⁺>Cl⁻> Mg²⁺>HCO₃⁻>Total Iron> K⁺ suggesting saline intrusion into the aquifer, halite dissolution, evaporation, ion exchange due to mixing of

saline water with freshwater. High negative loadings (> -0.7) for pH and depth suggest the inverse relationship with pH and depth indicating lower pH due to the dissolution of acidic minerals as suggested by Stumm and Morgan (2013) and high salinity in shallower depths. Component 2 shows positive loadings of Total Iron and Silica, while PO_4^{3-} is retained in Component 3 alone with high negative loading. Implementation of HCA resulted in creating 4 distinct clusters. Cluster 1 included 9 samples with a mean depth and TDS of 105 m and 3743.33 mg/l, Cluster 2 included 11 samples with a mean depth and TDS of 206 m and 1140 mg/l, Cluster 3 included 4 samples with mean depth and TDS of 54 m and 1373 mg/l respectively, while Cluster 4 retains only one sample with the lowest depth of 8.23 m and its distinct composition.

Figure 1: Piper Trilinear Diagram reflecting hydrochemistry respective of aquifer depth

Dominant hydrochemical facies identified by interpreting Piper plots are i) Na-Cl, ii) Na-Cl- HCO_3 , iii) Na- HCO_3 and iv) mixed type (Figure 1). Distribution of water types in distinct clusters are also analyzed and subjected to relevant interpretation.

4. CONCLUSION

The governing factors determined as saltwater intrusion, predominantly in shallower aquifers, the mixing of saline water with freshwater and the existence of freshwater at higher depths indicate shallower aquifer systems most vulnerable to saline intrusion and deeper aquifers with freshwater storage predominantly influenced by geochemical interactions. The vulnerability of shallower aquifers being more prone to salinity can and might be attributed to the higher extraction rate of groundwater as suggested by Nisi et al. (2022), evaporation effects in coastal regions, and land-use patterns as concluded by Rahman et al. (2018), dominated by shrimp culture with brackish water. As this study fills the gap of unexplored hydrochemistry of the Koyra region, it opens the gateway for development of the area's hydrogeochemical modelling and salinity management.

5. REFERENCES

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